

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: James-Civetta****FIRST NAME: Gloria****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium.

The author used the following software: MS Office Professional Plus on Windows 10.

THE ROAD TO BETTER WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

As lawyers, writing letters of advice, expert opinions, affidavits, opening statements and written submissions form an integral part of our lives. From the law (de jure) perspective, excellent legal writing can put forth a winning argument. Regularly, there have been complaints by judges about the quality of lawyers' written works. On the face of it (prima facie), for me to get to where I want to be, I need to improve my writing. Having enrolled myself for the DMCR programme, EUCLID's ACA-401D coursepack period 1 is where I begin. It consists of guidelines, checklists, reading materials, a video guide, templates, samples and book references; all essentials in the roadmap to not only writing better but being effective in developing one's writing as a thesis student. The first student orientation note puts one in check and balance on EUCLID's expectation and strict compliance on the use of the Word templates and how to name your saved documents. EUCLID's study instructions emphasis *the material that is provided must be carefully studied*. The abundance of information can seem overwhelming thus, *it is recommended to use a highlighter and to take notes* as you read along. Having chosen my five key concepts, I now embark on my first response paper using EUCLID's recommended Chicago Rules (Turabian) (EUCLID 2019, 24).

2) THE WRITING FOCUS

It is important to showcase that one has carefully studied the materials supplied by EUCLID. My chosen concepts begin with basics of essay writing, style guide, CMS crib sheet, use of commas and quotations. I acknowledge that essay writing is not a linear process (EUCLID 2019, 1). One needs to set aside time to read, research, analyse, think

and write a preliminary essay plan. The essence of an academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence (ibid.). To focus on your essay writing, you need to reflect with self-checking questions i.e., *what do you know of the topic; what do I need to read; is this material enough and can I use this material* (EUCLID 2019, 2).

In my career, where legal writing is a necessity in a professional capacity, I am reminded that the structure of a good essay requires a framework starting with an introduction, body and conclusion (EUCLID 2019, 3). When writing an academic paper, the introduction paragraph is where you provide a summary or roadmap of your thesis. As you seamlessly move to the body, develop your thesis with sub-paragraphs with each discussing your knowledge, the evidence, examples and authoritative quotes. When you conclude your essay, reconnect with your readers by summarising the main points with your take on the thesis' findings.

As having a style guide is an invaluable tool (EUCLID 2019, 25), Strunk's 'The Elements of Style', the Economist style guide and the Chicago Manual of Style are good examples of a starting point for a writer. However, I am reminded that legal writing is founded on the art of persuasion in the form on an argument. The fundamentals of a winning argument lie in cultivating good writing style and habits. In the words of Justice Choo Han Teck, *the understated style is usually more persuasive than the forceful, belligerent rhetoric that appears to draw attention to the lawyer and not the client and his case* (Choo 2018, 3).

a) Breaking down the components

The DNA to writing better starts with the rules of thumb, i.e., state the main thesis, stay focused on your topic, avoid sweeping statements, develop the knack of writing clearly, avoid clumsy or boring statements, support the thesis with assertions, taking views seriously and not plagiarising.

Knowing where to put the comma, when to use the quotation, expressing in either passive or active voice, using verb or adjective, a noun or pronoun and when to omit unnecessary words are essential reminders to a writer (EUCLID 2019, 18).

b) Art of good writing

Begin with reading EUCLID's Chapter 7 on Sample Corrections to Papers, where you learn how not to make mistakes in a response paper. As you read on you will note that the word 'serious' is to be avoided in academic papers and to opt for 'threatening' or 'unsettling'(EUCLID 2019, 36). A descriptive word appearing twice in back to back sentence structures is frowned upon. A sentence consisting of only five words is viewed as a bit too short (EUCLID 2019, 37) whilst a lengthy sentence of four lines is to be broken in two sentences.

Making CMS Crib Sheet your Holy Grail to the art of good writing is a must for any writer. The type of style, fonts, page formatting, use of end/footnotes, when to

abbreviate, where capitalisation applies, types of headings, when does one spell out numbers or use numerals, are rules to adhere.

i) *Key takeaways*

Once you have finished writing, do not forget to read your paper aloud (EUCLID 2019, 17). As you read, you might be drawn to faults in your statements or wrong choice of words. Sometimes putting aside the essay and coming back to it can result in further changes made positively.

Using Grammarly Premium to check your essay is recommended. You can also opt to rely on the good old-fashioned style of referring to Webster's Third New International Dictionary and its chief abridgement, Merriam-Webster's Collegiate Dictionary (EUCLID 2019, 44).

It is important to be consistent when writing using either American or British English. As I am from Singapore, a country from Southeast Asia, though British English is the official language in Singapore, I am also exposed to "Singlish" a colloquial Singaporean English. Being married to an Australian, I am influenced by "Aussie" English. What is commonly known as a chicken is 'chook' in Australia. Aussie footy is not rugby and what is soccer in British English is football in American English.

ii) *Key observations*

The first, coursepack for period one begins with the recommended citation to use in-text referencing to read '(EUCLID 2019, page no.)' whereas the article 'How to Write a Response Paper (RP)' cites '(EUCLID 2020, page no.)' instead. As such do not be confused and stick to the citation to be used as recommended by Euclid University.

The second, how to acknowledge authors. I note a difference, 'Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma' for the reference list whereas for the footnote it reads 'Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma'.

Finally, coursepack for period one features an 'Important Notice' alerting one to be observant of the intentional mistakes left therein, with the sole purpose of encouraging a EUCLID's student to point out the inaccuracies (EUCLID 2019, II).

3) CONCLUSION

Having studied EUCLID's coursepack period 1, I highlighted and underlined the requirements and academic writing techniques and made notes in my exercise book. As I aspire to henceforth cultivate good writing habits on my road to the final product – my thesis, I will not hesitate to reread and use the newfound writing tools and software programmes. I can now call Grammarly, Turabian and Word, my new writing buddies. In

the next period, I look forward in welcoming Zotero, JSTORS and Questia to my new book club.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: EUCLID University.

Turabian, Kate L. 2018. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colombo, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. Fitzgerald, and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.

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<http://libraryguides.bennett.edu/home/writing/chicago-turabian-style/turabian-style-in-text-parenthetical-citations--reference-list> (accessed on 25 June 2020).

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